

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND PHARMACOLOGICAL
EFFECTS OF *HYPERICUM TRIQUETRIFOLIUM***

Ali Esmail Al-Snafi

Department of Pharmacology, College of Medicine, University of Thi qar, Iraq.

Cell: +9647801397994. E mail: aboahmad61@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Hypericum triquetrifolium contained many biologically active chemicals included acylphloroglucinols triquetrireboudin, triquetriborin, essential and volatile oils and many phenolic compounds. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* contained hyperforin 0.013 ± 0.000 and hypericin 0.020 ± 0.001 w/w%. Many phenolics were isolated from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* included chlorogenic acid, caffeoylquinic acid, p-coumaroylquinic acid, epicatechin, rutin, hyperoside, 13,118-biapigenin, isoquercetine, quercitrine, quercetine, quercetin galactoside, quercetin rutinoside, quercetin-3-O-galactoside, kaempferol-3-O-glycoside, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, kaempferol and amentoflavone. The pharmacological studies showed that *Hypericum triquetrifolium* possessed antiinflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant, cytotoxic, antimicrobial and vasorelaxant effects. This review will highlight the chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*.

Keywords: Chemical constituents, pharmacology, *Hypericum triquetrifolium***Corresponding author:****Ali Esmail Al-Snafi**

Department of Pharmacology,

College of Medicine,

University of Thi qar, Iraq

Cell: +9647801397994.

E mail: aboahmad61@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ali Esmail Al-Snafi., *Chemical Constituents and Pharmacological Effects of Hypericum Triquetrifolium*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Herbal medicine is the oldest form of healthcare known to mankind. Herbs had been used by all cultures throughout history. The World Health Organization [WHO] estimates that 80 percent of the world populations presently use herbal medicine for some aspect of primary health care. However, plants are still providing some of our most valuable medicines [1-35].

Acylphloroglucinols triquetrireboudin, triquetriborin, essential and volatile oils and many phenolic compounds were isolated from *H. triquetrifolium*. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* contained hyperforin 0.013 ± 0.000 and hypericin 0.020 ± 0.001 w/w%. Many phenolics were isolated from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* included chlorogenic acid, caffeoylquinic acid, p-coumaroylquinic acid, epicatechin, rutin, hyperoside, I3,II8-biapigenin, isoquercetine, quercitrine, quercetine, quercetin galactoside, quercetin rutinoside, quercetin-3-O-galactoside, kaempferol-3-O-glycoside, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, kaempferol and amentoflavone. The pharmacological studies showed that *Hypericum triquetrifolium* possessed antiinflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant, cytotoxic, antimicrobial and vasorelaxant effects. This review was designed to highlight the chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*.

Plant profile:

Synonyms: *Hypericum crispum* [43].

Taxonomic classification:

Kingdom: Plantae, **Subkingdom:** Viridiplantae, **Infrakingdom:** Streptophyta, **Superdivision:** Embryophyta, **Division:** Tracheophyta, **Subdivision:** Spermatophytina, **Class:** Magnoliopsida, **Superorder:** Rosanae, **Order:** Malpighiales, **Family:** Hypericaceae, **Genus:** *Hypericum*, **Species:** *Hypericum triquetrifolium* [44-45].

Common names:

Arabic: Roja, Bu krad, Dathi or Nabat Yohanna; **English:** tangled hypericum [46-47].

Distribution:

It was distributed in Africa [Algeria, Libya, Tunisia]; Asia [Iran, Iraq, Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey]; Europe [Albania, Former Yugoslavia, Greece, Italy, Malta, France, Gibraltar, Spain][46].

Description:

It is a perennial herb to 50 cm high with a dense tangle of thin branches, glabrous but spotted with small black glands. Sap is resinous. It has deep vertical roots and a shallow rhizome system from which new shoots are produced. Leaves are opposite,

sessile, simple, 5–15 mm long, the base clasping the stem. Margins of the leaf are wavy, undulate, also with small black or translucent glands. Flowers are 10–15 mm across, shortly stalked in clusters of two to five at the ends of branches, with 5 free yellow petals. Stamens are many in three groups. Sepals are 2 mm long, ovate, without glands. The capsule is three-celled, 3–5 mm long with numerous seeds 1–2 mm long, slightly curved, with a pitted surface [48].

Traditional uses:

Hypericum triquetrifolium was used in traditional Arab herbal medicine to treat various inflammatory diseases and as sedative, astringent, anti-spasmodic, for intestine and bile disorders and poisoning [47, 49-50]. It was used in Turkish folk medicine in the treatment of bile and intestinal ailments [51-52].

Chemical constituents:

Hyperforin, hypericin and pseudohypericin are the active markers of *Hypericum* extract. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* contained hyperforin 0.013 ± 0.000 w/w% and hypericin 0.020 ± 0.001 w/w% [52, 53-54].

Hypericin was determined in different parts [leaf, flower and stem] of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* the percents of hypericin in leaves, flowers and stems were 310, 210 and 150 mg/100g, respectively [55].

The variation in the content of hyperforin, hypericin and pseudohypericin was studied in *Hypericum triquetrifolium* growing wild in four locations of Turkey. Hyperforin content ranged from 0.05 to 0.56 mg/g, hypericin from 0.74–1.98 mg/g, and pseudohypericin from 0.72–2.26 mg/g, dry weight. Among the different plant parts, the flowers were found to be the principle organ for hyperforin accumulation, while hypericin and pseudohypericin were accumulated mainly in leaves [51].

Two new acylphloroglucinols triquetrireboudin and triquetriborin were isolated from the petroleum ether extract of the aerial parts of *H. triquetrifolium* [56].

Many phenolics were isolated from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* included chlorogenic acid, caffeoylquinic acid, p-coumaroylquinic acid, epicatechin, rutin, hyperoside, I3,II8-biapigenin, isoquercetine, quercitrine, quercetine, quercetin galactoside, quercetin rutinoside, quercetin-3-O-galactoside, kaempferol-3-O-glycoside, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, kaempferol and amentoflavone [49, 57-61].

Chlorogenic acid, rutin, hyperoside, quercitrin, quercetin, and isoquercetin contents [mg/g dry weight] in vegetative stage of wild-growing

Hypericum triquetrifolium whole plant were 4.45 , 2.47 , 3.22 , 4.52, 0.36 , 17.49; in floral budding stage were 6.86, 5.93, 9.32, 7.64, 0.92, 24.65; in full flowering stage were 7.84, 3.61, 15.67, 7.98, 0.64, 7.33; in fresh fruiting stage were 3.48, 1.22, 5.93, 5.68, 0.62, 9.10; in mature fruiting stage were 0.33, 0.14, 0.37, 0.29, 0.39, 1.38, respectively. While, chlorogenic acid, rutin, hyperoside, quercitrin, quercetin, and isoquercetin contents [mg/g dry weight] in vegetative stage of of green house grown *Hypericum triquetrifolium* whole plant were 2.20 , 0.36, 1.31, 0.61, 0.66, 3.27; in floral budding stage were 9.07, 1.03, 3.31, 1.05, 0.36, 15.01; in full flowering stage were 6.06, 1.52, 3.96, 1.49, 0.99, 15.46; in fresh fruiting stage were 4.58, 1.19, 2.89, 0.51, 0.35, 11.03; in mature fruiting stage were 0.44, 0.04, 0.19, 0.27, 0.27, 0.23, respectively [62].

On the other hand, the plant parts were significantly varied in phenolic content. Among different plant parts, the flowers were found to be the principle organ for chlorogenic acid, hyperoside, apigenin-7-O-glucoside, kaempferol, quercetin and amentoflavone accumulations, while rutin and quercitrin were accumulated mainly in the leaves [61].

Fungal extracts of *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and commercial yeast were added to a liquid MS medium at 0.1, 0.25, 0.5 or 0.75 mg/l. Data showed that the yield of p-OH-benzoic acid and chlorogenic acid in cultures derived from leaf of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* [LCs] treated with 0.5 mg/l yeast extract increased significantly compared with the control. Caffeic acid and tannic acid decreased in LCs significantly after elicitation with all biotic elicitors, but catechin accumulation in LCs increased significantly, when *A. niger* extract was added at all concentrations. Rutin, hypersoid and quercetin production in cultures derived from stem of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* [SCs] increased significantly when treated with the fungal elicitors; *A. niger*, *F. oxysporum* and yeast extracts. Chlorogenic decreased significantly in SCs, after the addition of all biotic elicitors at different concentrations [63].

N-nonane [15%], germacrene-D [13%], caryophyllene oxide [12%], b-caryophyllene [11%], a-pinene [10%], myrcene [5%], b-pinene [4%] and sabinene [3%] were the main components of the oil of *H. triquetrifolium* from Italy [64].

1-Hexanal [18.8%], 3-methylnonane [12.5%], α -pinene [12.3%], caryophyllene oxide [4.7%], 2-methyldecane [4.5%] and α -amorphenone [4.2%] were the main components of the essential oil of the aerial parts of *H. triquetrifolium* from Turkey [65].

α -humulene, *cis*-calamenene, δ -cadinene, bicyclogermacrene, eremophilene, β -caryo-phyllene, [E]- γ -bisabolene and α -pinene were the main components of the Tunisian *H. triquetrifolium* oil [66].

However, the essential oil of the aerial parts of Tunisian *Hypericum triquetrifolium* obtained by ultrasound extraction, hydrodistillation and Soxhlet/dynamic headspace were analyzed by GC-FID and GC-MS showed the predominance of *n*-octane, α -pinene, β -caryophyllene, 2-methyloctane, *n*-nonane, germacrene- D, α -selinene and β -cubebene [67].

Germacrene-D [21.7%], β -caryophyllene [18.3%], δ -cadinene [6.4%], *trans*- β -farnesene [4.3%], α -humulene [3.8%], β -selinene [3.7%], γ -cadinene [3.3%] and *trans*-phytol [3.2%] were found to be the major constituents of the oil of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* from Iran. The oil of *H. triquetrifolium* consisted of five monoterpene hydrocarbons [3.4%], two oxygenated monoterpenes [0.4%], twenty-two sesquiterpene hydrocarbons [77.1%], eight oxygenated sesquiterpenes [7.9%] and one oxygenated diterpene [3.2%]. Twelve nonterpenic compounds were also consisted 5.1% of the oil [68].

Hexenal, [E] [12.63%], Octane, 2, 3, 3-trimethyl [11.36%], Pentadecane, 7-methyl- [9.7%], Undecane [6.15%] and alpha. -Pinene [5.75%] were the main components of the essential oil of *H. triquetrifolium* from Iraq [69].

The crude methanolic extract of the aerial parts of *H. triquetrifolium* was examined for its potential activity in counteracting and preventing cognition impairment caused by acute and chronic restrain stress in rats. *H. triquetrifolium* methanolic extracts were administrated intraperitoneally [50 mg/Kg]. Rats were tested for spatial memory in radial arm water maze test. Results revealed that chronic psychosocial stress impairs short term memory. Acute stress also impairs both short term memory and long term memory. Chronic *H. triquetrifolium* extract administration prevented stress induced memory impairment in both chronic and acute stressed rats which is confirmed by the correction of stress-induced reduction in BDNF protein levels especially in the hippocampal area of brain [59].

Pharmacological effects:

Antinflammatory and analgesic effects:

The antiinflammatory effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* was evaluated in rat model of

carrageenan induced inflammation. Male Wistar rats were treated intraperitoneally with 0.4% dimethylsulphoxide [DMSO] [as control group] and *H. triquetrifolium* extract [25, 50, 60 mg/kg], 30 min before 0.1 ml 1% carrageenan injection. Paw volume was measured before and 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 h after the injection of carrageenan. Intraperitoneal administration of *H. triquetrifolium* extract [25, 50, 60 mg/kg] inhibited paw swelling dose-dependently at 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 h after carrageenan injection [$P < 0.05$]. We can conclude that *H. triquetrifolium* extract may exert an anti-inflammatory effect in rats. # 2002 Elsevier Science Ireland Ltd. All rights reserved [70].

The anti-inflammatory mechanism of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* was studied by measuring the expression and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, tumor necrosis factor- α [TNF- α] and interleukine-6 [IL-6], and inducible nitric oxide synthase [iNOS] in human monocytic cells, THP-1. The effects were assessed by measuring the levels of secretory proteins and mRNA of TNF- α and IL-6, the levels of nitric oxide [NO] secretion and the expression of iNOS in THP-1 cells. Cells were treated with 5 μ g lipopolysaccharide/ml [LPS] in the presence and absence of increasing concentrations of extracts from the aerial parts of *H. triquetrifolium*. During the entire experimental period, extract was used in concentrations [up to 250 μ g/ml] that had no cytotoxic effects, measured with MTT and LDH assays. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extracts remarkably suppressed the LPS-induced NO release, significantly attenuated the LPS-induced transcription of iNOS and inhibited in a dose-dependent manner the expression and release of TNF- α . No significant effects were observed on the release of IL-6 [50].

The anti-inflammatory activity of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extracts [HT-extract] was evaluated on lipopolysaccharide-stimulated human monocytic [THP-1] cells and human peripheral blood mononuclear cells [PBMCs]. The expression and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines tumor necrosis factor- α [TNF- α] and interleukin 6 [IL-6], as well as the anti-inflammatory cytokine interleukin 10 [IL-10] were evaluated by assessing the levels of proteins and mRNA's of TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-10 in both cell types. Cells were exposed to 5 μ g lipopolysaccharide [LPS] /ml in the absence and presence of increasing concentrations of 50% ethanol extracts from the aerial parts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. The anti-inflammatory efficacy experiments were performed with HT-extract concentrations up to 250 μ g/ml that had no cytotoxic effects as assessed with MTT and LDH assays. HT-

extract remarkably inhibited the expression and secretion of TNF- α and IL-6 at a concentration of 250 μ g/ml. HT-extract remarkably elevated IL-10 secretion and mRNA levels at 125 μ g/ml. Furthermore, HT-extract exhibited relatively high antioxidant activity [IC₅₀ of 5 μ g/ml] as measured with DPPH assay [71].

The antinociceptive activity of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* lyophilized extract was investigated in mice. Formalin paw test and tail flick tests were used for the evaluation of the antinociceptive activity. The extracts caused a significant dose-related inhibition of the first phase [50, 60 mg/kg, ip] and second phase [10, 25, 50 and 60 mg/kg, ip] of formalin induced hindpaw licking. Additionally, the extract administration [50, 60 mg/kg, ip] increased the tail flick latencies. No significant change was observed in any of the treatment groups in the sensorimotor performance test [72].

Antioxidant effect:

The total phenolic content of the aqueous extract of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* was 44.6 mgGE/g dry weight, and methanolic extract was 40.6 mgGE/g dry. The antioxidant activity of the aqueous extract was 457.4 mmol TE/g dry weights, and methanolic extract was 535.5 mmol TE/g dry weights [73].

The phenolic compounds extracted from the aerial parts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* showed strong antioxidant activity as tested using an in vitro method based on sodium arachidonate, bleomycin and thiobarbituric acid with alpha-tocopherol as the reference solution. The antioxidant investigation of the methanol extract of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* aerial part, revealed that IC₅₀ between 0.062 and 1 mg/ml [49, 57].

The antioxidant effect of 80% methanolic extract of *H. Triquetrifolium* [whole plant] was investigated using in vitro antioxidant assays were used: total antioxidant capacity, DPPH free radical scavenging, ferric reducing, ferrous chelating, total phenols and flavonoids. Among 12 tested plant extracts, *H. triquetrifolium* extracts possessed the highest total antioxidant capacity, the highest DPPH free radical scavenging activity and the highest reducing power [74].

The antioxidative potential of the ethanol extracts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* was investigated using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl [DPPH], metal chelating, reducing power, hydroxyl radical, total antioxidant activity, and lipid peroxidation inhibition assays. The extract was found to be highly active in

the DPPH radical scavenging assay with IC₅₀ of 39.0 µg/ml. The ethanol extracts exhibited a high reducing power, suggesting that the extract had strong electron-donating capacity. The degradation of deoxyribose by hydroxyl radicals was shown to be inhibited by the extract, mainly by scavenging hydroxyl radicals rather than as chelators of iron ions. The total antioxidant activity of ethanol was comparable with vitamin E [75].

The ability of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* to prevent oxidative damage to bovine serum albumin [BSA] induced by Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ and ascorbic acid was investigated. The ethanol extracts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* at different concentrations [50-1,000 µg/ml] efficiently prevented protein oxidation induced by hydroxy radical as assayed by protein oxidation markers including protein carbonyl formation and polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. The effect of ethanol extract of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* on DNA cleavage induced by UV-photolysis of H₂O₂ using pBluescript M13+ plasmid DNA was also investigated. The extract significantly inhibited DNA damage induced by reactive oxygen species [ROS] [76].

Cytotoxic and genotoxic effects:

The Sulforodamine B [SRB] assay was used to test cytotoxicity of antioxidant constituents isolated from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* against four human cancer cell lines and one normal cell line, large cell lung carcinoma cell line COR-L23, the hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG-2, renal cell adenocarcinoma ACHN, the amelanotic melanoma cell line C32 and normal human foetal lung MRC5. The results showed that I3-II8-biapiogenin exhibited strong cytotoxic activity [IC₅₀ = 5.73 micro g mL⁻¹] showing a certain degree of selectivity against the different cell types [77].

Two cancer cell lines: Colon and Lung [HCT-116, A549] and one normal [control] cell line [skeletal muscle, L6] were selected to test the efficacy of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* different extracts in apoptosis induction. The cells were treated with an increasing concentration of [distilled water, 50% water- 50% ethanol, and hexane] plant extract [0, 8, 16, 32, 62, 125, 250, 500, 1000 and 2000µg/ml] for 24h. Then MTT assay was used to test cytotoxicity of the extracts. The results showed that *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extracts induced apoptosis in colon cancer cell line [HCT116], muscle cell line [L6], and lung cancer cell line [A549] at the concentration of 500µg/ml through mitochondrial dependent pathway by releasing cytochrome c [78]. The cytotoxic effect was investigated using Vero cell lines. They showed

low cytotoxic effect [CC₅₀ ranged between 0.58 mg/ml and 12.00 mg/ml] [79].

Hypericum triquetrifolium aqueous extract were studied for its toxic and the possible clastogenic effects in vivo on the bone marrow and spermatozoa cells of Swiss albino mice. The lethal dose of the aqueous extract was considered to be 10.33 g/kg of the body weight, injected subcutaneously. *H. triquetrifolium* extract induce statistically significant increases in the average numbers of micronucleus [MN] at the dose 2 g/kg and chromosome aberrations at the doses 2 and 1 g/kg, the majority of aberrations observed were chromatid breaks, centromeric breaks, acentric fragments. The extract was found to inhibit mitotic index [MI] in a dose-dependent manner. Moreover the plant extract showed a significant induction of sperm abnormalities in all concentrations used [2, 1, and 0.25 g/kg] comparing with the untreated animals. The most frequent types of sperm abnormalities of the treated groups were; amorphous, pseudo-droplet defect, bent mid piece defect and corkscrew mid piece defect. However, the lowest dose 0.25 g/kg body weight was the most effective one which markedly increased the corkscrew midpiece defect. The results indicated that the mixture of the compounds found in the aqueous extract caused cytotoxicity and induced different cytogenetic effects in both somatic and germ cell [47]

Antimicrobial effects:

Methanolic extract was active against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*; acetone extract was active against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Staphylococcus aureus*; CHCL₃ extract was active against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* [80-82].

The essential oils of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* from five different Tunisian localities [Fondouk DJedid, Bou Arada, Bahra, Fernana and Dhrea Ben Jouder] were evaluated for their antimicrobial activities against bacterial and fungal strains [*Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio alginolyticus*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium solani*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Candida albicans*, *Candida glabrata* and *Candida krusei*]. The results showed a good antibacterial activity against a wide range of bacterial strains, MIC values ranging between 0.39-

12.50 mg/ml and MBC values between 1.56-25.0 mg/ml. The essential oils showed antifungal activity with MIC values ranging between 0.39 µg/ml and 12.50 µg/ml; MFC values ranged between 3.12 µg/ml and 25.00 µg/ml. The essential oils did not show antiviral activity against coxsackievirus B3[79].

Five extracts and pure compounds from the aerial parts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* were tested for antibacterial activity against 31 gram-positive and gram-negative strains using the agar dilution method. The ethyl acetate extract exhibited a weak antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus strains, quercetin and I3,I8-biapigenin were the active components of the extract [83].

H. triquetrifolium showed antibacterial and antifungal activities with diameter of growth inhibition of [10-16mm]: *Escherichia coli K12* [12 mm, 60µg/disc], *Escherichia coli PBR322* [10 mm, 40µg/disc], *Escherichia coli PUC9* [10 mm, 40µg/disc], *Bacillus brevis ATCC*[10 mm, 40µg/disc], *Bacillus cereus DM65*[12 mm,40µg/disc], *Streptococcus pyogenes DM41*[12 mm, 40µg/disc], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa DMC66* [12 mm,40µg/disc], *Staphylococcus aureus DMC70* [16 mm,40µg/disc] and *Candida albicans DM31*[12 mm,40µg/disc][84].

The protective effect:

The possible protective effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* [HT] was investigated against cyclophosphamide [CP] -induced hepatotoxicity. The results revealed that 25, 50 and 100 mg/kg HT, caused an important decrease in the [CP] toxicity. In the groups given both CP plus HT, there was a rise in serum total anti-oxidant status levels, while the levels of AST, ALT, ALP, LDH, TOS and OSI showed a remarkable decrease. Liver histological gave further evidence for the protective effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* [85].

Vasorelaxant effect:

The vasorelaxant effect of the total extract of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* was investigated on rat isolated aortic rings. Contractions with phenylephrine and KC1 were compared after the tissues were incubated with different concentrations of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extract. In addition, the inhibitory effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extract [105-103 g/ml] on the sustained contractions of aorta with phenylephrine and KG was also investigated. The maximal inhibition obtained by the extract for the phenylephrine contractions was 93.95 ± 5.23%, while the maximal inhibition was found as 85.78 ± 4.87 % for KC1 contractions. However, *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extract inhibited both phenylephrine

and KC1 induced contractions in a concentration-dependent manner [86].

Toxicity:

The lethal dose of the aqueous extract was considered to be 10.33 g/kg of the body weight, injected subcutaneously in mice [47].

CONCLUSION:

The review highlighted the chemical constituent, pharmacological and therapeutic effects of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* as promising source of drugs because of its safety and effectiveness.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Snafi AE, Wajdy JM and Tayseer Ali Talab. Galactagogue action of *Nigella sativa* seeds. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2014; 4[6]: 58-61.
2. Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Citrullus colocynthis* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[3]: 57-67.
3. Al-Snafi AE. Medical importance of *Cichorium intybus* - A review IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[3]: 41-56.
4. Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological importance of *Clitoria ternatea* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[3]: 68-83.
5. Al-Snafi AE. The medical Importance of *Cicer arietinum* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[3]: 29-40.
6. Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacological activities of *Cuminum cyminum* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 46-65.
7. Al-Snafi AE. Medical importance of *Cupressus sempervirens*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 66-76.
8. Al-Snafi AE. The contents and pharmacology of *Crotalaria juncea*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 77-86.
9. Al-Snafi AE. The medical importance of *Cydonia oblonga*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 87-99.
10. Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacology of *Crocus sativus*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 8-38.
11. Al-Snafi AE. The chemical constituents and therapeutic importance of *Cressa cretica*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 39-46.
12. Al-Snafi AE. The Pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Cordia myxa*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 47-57.
13. Al-Snafi AE. The contents and pharmacological importance of *Corchorus capsularis*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 58-63.

14. Al-Snafi AE. The chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Convolvulus arvensis* and *Convolvulus scammonia*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[6]: 64-75.
15. Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Cynodon dactylon*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 17-31.
16. Al-Snafi AE. A review on *Cyperus rotundus* A potential medicinal plant. IOSR Journal Of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 32-48.
17. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants with antidiabetic effects [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 49-61.
18. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants with antioxidant and free radical scavenging effects [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal Of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 62-82.
19. Al-Snafi AE. A review on chemical constituents and pharmacological activities of *Coriandrum sativum*. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 17-42.
20. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants with cardiovascular effects [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 43-62.
21. Al-Snafi AE. Detoxification capacity and protective effects of medicinal plants [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 63-84.
22. Al-Snafi AE. Beneficial medicinal plants in digestive system disorders [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[7]: 85-92.
23. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants with central nervous effects [part 2]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[8]: 52-75.
24. Al-Snafi AE. Nutritional value and pharmacological importance of citrus species grown in Iraq. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[8]: 76-108.
25. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants affected male and female fertility [part 1]- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[10]: 11-26.
26. Al-Snafi AE. Antiparasitic effects of medicinal plants [part 1]- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[10]: 51-66.
27. Al-Snafi AE. Antimicrobial effects of medicinal plants [part 3]: plant based review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2016; 6[10]: 67-92.
28. Al-Snafi AE. A review on *Dodonaea viscosa*: A potential medicinal plant. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]: 10-21.
29. Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacology and medical importance of *Dolichos lablab* [*Lablab purpureus*]- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]: 22-30.
30. Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacology of *Equisetum arvense*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]: 31-42.
31. Al-Snafi AE. Nutritional and therapeutic importance of *Daucus carota*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]: 72-88.
32. Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Dalbergia sissoo* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]: 59-71.
33. Al-Snafi AE. Medical importance of *Datura fastuosa* [syn: *Datura metel*] and *Datura stramonium* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[2]:43-58.
34. Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacology and therapeutic potential of *Euphorbia hirta* [Syn: *Euphorbia pilulifera*] - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 7-20.
35. Al-Snafi AE. A review on *Fagopyrum esculentum*: A potential medicinal plant. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 21-32.
36. Al-Snafi AE. Nutritional and pharmacological importance of *Ficus carica* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 33-48.
37. Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacology of *Ficus religiosa*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 49-60.
38. Al-Snafi AE. Chemical contents and medical importance of *Dianthus caryophyllus*- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 61-71.
39. Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Eucalyptus* species grown in Iraq. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[3]: 72-91.
40. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants possessed antioxidant and free radical scavenging effects [part 3]- A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[4]: 48-62.
41. Al-Snafi AE. Anticancer effects of Arabian medicinal plants [part 1] - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[4]: 63-102.
42. Al-Snafi AE. Medicinal plants for prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017; 7[4]: 103-163.
43. The plant list, *Hypericum triquetrifolium*, <http://www.theplantlist.org/tp1.1/record/kew-2859086>
44. Catalogue of Life, *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. <http://www.catalogueoflife.org/col/details/species/id/f3143343bfddbcbef36883185d0ac8b> [30 June 2017].
45. ITIS, *Hypericum*, https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=21454#null

46. US National plant germplasm system, *Hypericum triquetrifolium*, <https://npgsweb.ars-grin.gov/gringlobal/taxonomydetail.aspx?id=403469>
47. Mohammed BMA and Kheravii SKQ. Evaluation of genotoxic potential of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extract in somatic and germ cells of male albino mice AGRIS since 2012; 1[4]: 231-239.
48. WSSA, *Hypericum triquetrifolium*, <http://wssa.net/wp-content/uploads/Hypericum-triquetrifolium.pdf>
49. Couladis M, Baziou P, Verykokidou E and Loukis A. Antioxidant activity of polyphenols from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. *Phytother Res* 2002; 16[8]:769-770.
50. Saad B, AbouAtta BS, Basha W, Hmade A, Kmail A, Khasib S and Said O. *Hypericum triquetrifolium*—derived factors downregulate the production levels of LPS-induced nitric oxide and tumor necrosis factor- α in THP-1 Cells. *Hindawi Publishing Corporation Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 2011, doi:10.1093/ecam/nen056
51. Çamaş N, Radušienė J, Ayana AK, Çırak C, Janulis V and Ivanauskas L. Variation of bioactive secondary metabolites in *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra from wild populations of Turkey. *Natural Product Communications* Vol. 3 [10] 2008 1713-1717.
52. Baytop T. *Therapy with Medicinal Plants in Turkey*. Istanbul University Press, İstanbul, 1999:66-167.
53. Bauer S, Störmer E, Graubaum HJ and Roots I. Determination of hyperforin, hypericin, and pseudohypericin in human plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography analysis with fluorescence and ultraviolet detection. *Journal of Chromatography* 2001;765, 29-35.
54. Tawaha K, Gharaibeh M, El-Elimat T and Alali FQ. Determination of hypericin and hyperforin content in selected Jordanian *Hypericum* species. *Industrial Crops and Products* 2010; 32: 241-245.
55. Aghel N, Ramezani Z and Jalalitalab H. Isolation and determination of hypericins from different parts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra grown in Khozestan by UV/Visible spectrophotometry. *Jundishapur Scientific Medical Journal* 2012; 11[3]: 285.
56. Volkov I, Schmidt S and Heilmann J. Isolation and structure elucidation of acylphloroglucinols from *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. *Planta Med* 2015; 81 - 85. DOI: 10.1055/s-0035-1565462
57. Conforti F, Statti AG, Tundis R, Menichini F and Houghton P. Antioxidant activity of methanolic extract of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra aerial part. *Fitoterapia* 2002;73:479-483
58. Cirak C, Radusiene J, Aksoy HM and Mackinaite R. Differential phenolic accumulation in two *Hypericum* species in response to inoculation with *Diploceras hypericinum* and *Pseudomonas putida*. *Plant Protect Sci* 2014; 50[3]: 119–128.
59. Al.Hafiz LSS. Phytochemical analysis of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra and assessment of its effect on cognitive impairment caused by chronic restrain and/or acute stress. MSc thesis, Faculty of Graduate Studies Jordan University of Science and Technology 2009.
60. Karakashov B, Grigorakis S, Loupassaki S, Mourtzinis I and Makris DP. Optimisation of organic solvent-free polyphenol extraction from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra using Box–Behnken experimental design and kinetics. *Int J Ind Chem* 2015; 6:85–92.
61. Cirak C, Radusiene J, Janulis V, Ivanauskas L, Camas N and Ayan AK. Phenolic constituents of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra [Guttiferae] growing in Turkey: variation among populations and plant parts. *Turk J Biol* 2011; 35: 449-456.
62. Ciraki C, Radusiene J, Karpaviciene B, Camasi N and Odabas MS. Changes in phenolic content of wild and greenhouse-grown *Hypericum triquetrifolium* during plant development. *Turk J Agric* 2013; 37: 307-314.
63. Azezi HA and Ibrahim KM. Effect of biotic elicitors on secondary metabolite production in cell suspensions of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. *Bulletin UASVM Horticulture* 2013; 70[1]: 26-33.
64. Bertoli A, Menichini F, Mazzetti M, Spinelli G and Morelli I. Volatile constituents of the leaves and flowers of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. *Flav Frag J* 2003;18:91-94.
65. Yuce E and Bagci E. The essential oils of the aerial parts of two *Hypericum* taxa [*Hypericum triquetrifolium* and *Hypericum aviculariifolium* subsp. *depilatum* var. *depilatum* [Clusiaceae] from Turkey. *Nat Prod Res* 2011;26:1985-1990.
66. Karim H, Kamel M, Mouna BT, Thouraya C and Brahim M. Essential oil composition of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. aerial parts. *Ital J Biochem* 2007;56:40-46.
67. Hosni K, Msaada K, Chahed T, Ben Taarit M and Marzouk B. Comparative Analysis of the Essential Oils of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. Extracted by Ultrasound, Hydrodistillation and Soxhlet/Dynamic Headspace. *Medicinal and Aromatic Plant Science and Biotechnology* 2011; 5 [Special Issue 1]: 100-104.
68. Sajjadi SE, Mehregan I and Taheri M. Essential oil composition of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*

- Turra growing wild in Iran. Res Pharm Sci 2015; 10[1]: 90-94.
69. Azeez HA. Comparison between *Hypericum triquetrifolium* leaves and derived calli in essential oil content. Journal of Al-Nahrain University 2017; 20 [2]:123-130.
70. Ozturk B, Apaydin S, Goldeli E, Ince I and Zeybek U. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. Extract exhibits antiinflammatory activity in the rat. J Ethnopharmacol 2002;80:207-209.
71. Saad B, Embaslat WH, Abu-Farich B, Mahajna S, Azab M, et al. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* extracts modulate IL-6, IL-10 and TNF- α protein and mRNA expression in LPS-activated human peripheral blood mononuclear cells and THP-1-derived macrophages. Med Aromat Plants 2016; S3:004. doi:10.4172/2167-0412.S3-004.
72. Apaydin S, Zeybek U, Ince I, Elgin G, Karamenderes C, Ozturk B and Tuglular I. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. extract exhibits antinociceptive activity in the mouse. J Ethnopharmacol 1999;67:307-312.
73. Alalialab FQ, Tawahac K, El-Elimatb T, Syoufd M, El-Fayadd M, Abulailad K et al. Antioxidant activity and total phenolic content of aqueous and methanolic extracts of Jordanian plants: an ICBG project. Natural Product Research 2007; 21[12]:1121-1131.
74. Bilto YY, Alabdallat NG and Salim M. Antioxidant properties of twelve selected medicinal plants commonly used in Jordan. British Journal of Pharmaceutical Research 2015; 6[2]: 121-130.
75. Kızıl G, Kızıl M, Yavuz M, Emen S and Hakimoğlu F. Antioxidant activities of ethanol extracts of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. and *Hypericum scabroides*. Pharmaceutical Biology 2008; 26[4]: 231-242
76. Kızıl G, Kızıl M, and Ceken B. Protective ability of ethanol extracts of *Hypericum scabroides* Robson & Poulter and *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra against protein oxidation and DNA damage. Food Sci Biotechnol 2009;18[1]: 130-136.
77. Conforti F, Loizzo MR, Statti AG and Menichini F. Cytotoxic activity of antioxidant constituents from *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. Nat Prod Res 2007;21:42-46.
78. Tu`meh AMA. *In Vitro* Evaluation of apoptotic induction of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* and *Arum palaestinum* plant extracts on cancer cell lines. Faculty of Graduate Studies, An-Najah National University 2015.
79. Rouis Z, Abid N, Koudja S, Yangui T, Elaissi A, Cioni PL, Flamini G and Aouni M. Evaluation of the cytotoxic effect and antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral activities of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra essential oils from Tunisia. BMC activities of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra essential oils from Tunisia. BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine 2013, 13:24, <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1472-6882/13/24>
80. Alshamma A and Mitscher LA. Screening results of 327 species for alkaloids and antimicrobial agents. J. Natural Product 1979; 42: 633-642.
81. Sakara MK and Tamer AU. Antimicrobial activity of different extracts from some *Hypericum* species. Fitoterapia 1990; 61: 464-466.
82. Mukherjee PK, Wahile A, Ahamed KFHN and Rajan S. *Hypericum* source of natural antimicrobials. Oriental Pharmacy and Experimental Medicine 2003; 3[3]: 111-122.
83. Pistelli L, Bertoli A, Morelli I, Menichini F, Musmanno RA, Di Maggio T and Coratza G. Chemical and antibacterial evaluation of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra. Phytotherapy Res 2005;19: 787-791.
84. Kızıl G, Tokar Z, Özen H and Aytekin C. The Antimicrobial Activity of Essential Oils of *Hypericum scabrum*, *Hypericum scabroides* and *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. Phytotherapy Research 2004; 18: 339-341.
85. Cetik S, Keskin C and Ayhanci A. Protective effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra on cyclophosphamide induced hepatotoxicity in rat. 3rd World Congress on Pharmacology. Birmingham, UK. August 8-10, 2016.
86. Apaydin S, Gldeli E, Karamenderes C, Meral G, Zeybek U and Tuglular I. The Inhibitory effect of *Hypericum triquetrifolium* Turra extract on rat aortic smooth muscle contraction. T Klin J Med Res 2001; 19: 24-30.